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Abstract

Enteroviruses (EV) are a genus of the Picornaviridae family. About 70 serotypes have been isolated from humans. The name of this viral group comes from the place where they reproduce after entering the body - the intestines. They usually multiply in the lining of the gastrointestinal tract, where the infection may manifest sub-clinically or as a mild infection. In some cases, however, the virus spreads to various organs, where it causes severe disease. On the other hand, summer food poisoning is a microbial intoxication associated with the consumption of food contaminated with pathogenic bacterial microorganisms and their toxins, but viral food intoxications also occur. Summer food poisonings increase because warm weather accelerates the growth of microbes in perishable foods.

Keywords: Summer infections, children, complications, rehydration, strict hygiene.

Introduction.

Human enteroviruses include polioviruses, coxsackieviruses, echoviruses and new enteroviruses. Enterovirus infections are in most cases self-limiting, relatively mild diseases that last from 7 to 10 days, with the acute phase, when all symptoms are strongly expressed, usually lasting about 4-5 days^[4]. Humans are the only reservoir for enteroviruses. Carriers of the infection pose a danger to others from several weeks to 1-2 months after infection^[9,10,18]. Susceptibility is universal, but children and adolescents are mainly affected. Transmission occurs by various routes (most often fecal-oral), through consumption of contaminated water or food products, as well as with oral secretions of sick individuals. Less commonly, airborne droplets, as well as from the mother to the fetus (vertically)^[4,9,10,18]. The incubation period is 2-40 days. Recovery from infection leads to the development of life-long immunity^[9,18]. On the other hand, the most common food poisonings are due to the violation of basic hygiene standards and improper food storage are favorable factors for food contamination. Food is a good environment for the development of some pathogenic microorganisms and under appropriate conditions (high temperature and humidity) they multiply and cause food poisoning. The main causes of food poisoning are staphylococci, salmonellosis and colibacillosis. The toxins of some microbes such as staphylococci are resistant to boiling, which means that the risk of poisoning is high even with thermal processing. Most often, the transmission of salmonella toxicoinfection occurs when using meat, sausages, eggs, dairy products, ice cream and cakes contaminated with salmonella. Staphylococcal infection is caused by the formed staphylococcal enterotoxin. The main sources of this infection are humans (through the skin and nasopharynx) and animals suffering from mastitis - they contaminate fresh milk, and from there many dairy and confectionery products. A common source of staphylococcal infection is also contaminated foods - cakes, creams, ice cream, milk. Food contamination occurs upon contact with healthy asymptomatic carriers or patients with staphylococcal rhinitis or angina. Contamination of food products with colibacteria occurs mainly by humans through contaminated hands and food. Poisoning

can also occur after consuming foods that are not refrigerated, even though the appearance and taste of the food do not change - such foods include meat, eggs, and fish products. The source of coli-infection are sick and healthy carriers. The causative agent of botulism is a microorganism that forms spores and develops in an environment poor in oxygen - canned vegetables, sausages and fish. It is also often found in the soil, from where it gets into food, through unwashed vegetables. Usually the food looks spoiled, but it is possible that there are no changes and it is still infected. Botulinum toxin is believed to be the strongest natural toxin^[1,2].

Clinical picture.

The clinical course of EV infections.

Although many enterovirus infections are asymptomatic, some serotypes are inherently more pathogenic. The clinical course of enterovirus infections includes many clinical forms: "summer flu"; enterovirus exanthema; herpangina; "hand, foot, mouth" syndrome; pleurodynia; aseptic meningitis; encephalitis; paralytic disease; myocarditis and neonatal infections. The first four clinical forms occur most often in the form of epidemic outbreaks, each year one of them prevailing. While neuroinfections occur less frequently and generally have a benign course and usually end with recovery in 10-15 days.

In some cases, EV infections occur severely with high mortality, which is determined by the virulence of some serotypes of enteroviruses. Myocarditis and neonatal infections occur very rarely, but are very severe and usually end in death^[4,6,7,9,16-18].

Non-poliomyelitis EVs cause mild to severe inflammatory diseases in the central nervous system and respiratory tract. In most cases, those infected remain asymptomatic, but are involved in the spread of the infection - carrier status^[4,6,9]. The most common infections caused by non-poliomyelitis EVs occur as a flu-like illness - chills, headache, severe fatigue, general malaise, joint and muscle pain, and high fever that is difficult to control with medication. In some cases, vomiting, mild diarrhea, and abdominal pain are also observed. Therefore, these infections are called "summer flu"^[4,18]. 1-3 days later, a rash appears, starting on the face, spreading to the body and limbs, lasting from hours to several days. The nature of this enterovirus exanthema is polymorphic - spots, blisters, urticaria-like

skin changes, less often hemorrhages. The disease lasts 7-10 days and is caused by ECHO type 9 [4,9,18].

Clinical characteristics of food poisoning.

The most characteristic feature of food poisoning is their group nature, affecting multiple children who have consumed the same food. Symptoms of food poisoning usually appear two to six hours after consuming contaminated food and include fever and chills, nausea and vomiting, general weakness and fatigue, headache, abdominal cramps, and diarrhea that may contain blood. Food poisoning in most cases ends with recovery within a few days. In childhood, they are very dangerous and can lead to death. Coli-infection clinically occurs with colienteritis and is characterized by high fever, vomiting, diarrhea, dehydration and water-electrolyte disorders. Botulism is the most severe food poisoning and is often fatal^[1,2].

Diagnosics.

The diagnosis of summer viral and foodborne infections is based on the history of the disease, the characteristic clinical course and paraclinical examinations. In addition to the usual complete blood count, ESR and C-reactive protein (CRP), the following examinations are also performed:

- In severe cases of food poisoning, microbiological examination of vomited gastric contents and stool samples may need to be tested to identify the specific pathogen (such as Salmonella, Staphylococcus or E. coli).^[1,2]
- To diagnose the most common causes of viral gastroenteritis in childhood (rota, adeno-, astro- and noroviruses), a fecal sample is examined using rapid immunochromatographic tests.
- To diagnose EV infections, stool, throat secretions, and cerebrospinal fluid from patients are examined in the first days of the illness. Serological tests for the detection of antibodies are of no significant value, because specific antibodies for acute infection are formed slowly, in addition, a repeat test is required after 20 days, which will establish the presence of increasing levels of IgG antibodies^[4,9,18].
- Molecular methods are increasingly crucial^[6,16]. The RT-PCR method allows the detection of specific viral RNA, which proves the presence of the infection. RT-PCR is the most sensitive and widely used gold standard for diagnosing all human enterovirus infections – including polio, coxsackieviruses, echoviruses and newer strains such as EV-D68. It provides results much faster than traditional viral cell cultures and is more sensitive. Enteroviruses are cleared from the blood rapidly. PCR is very reliable for detecting viruses in cerebrospinal fluid (CSF) or respiratory specimens, but its diagnostic value decreases if tested too late in the infection. In some cases, stool testing (fecal PCR) is much more sensitive later in the disease. PCR for EV performed on throat swabs or feces is more sensitive than that performed on lumbar puncture^[6].

Treatment.

- Symptomatic treatment with analgesics, antiemetics and antipyretics is administered.
- Treatment of EV infections is nonspecific, supportive^[4,22]. In case of meningitis - symptomatic

treatment (intravenous immunoglobulins, corticosteroids and fluoxetine, suppressing the replication of EV B and D, but not A and C). In case of EV myocarditis, complications are prevented and treated - arrhythmias, pericardial effusions, heart failure^[9,18,22]. There is evidence that pleconaril reduces the severity of EV infections in newborns^[18].

- Although antibiotics are not usually used in viral food poisoning, they may be prescribed for specific bacterial infections. In the case of viral or bacterial gastrointestinal infections leading to dehydration, the main treatment is rehydration. The child should be given small, frequent sips of oral rehydration solution (ORS). Infants should continue to breastfeed or take formula as usual. Avoid giving the child milk, caffeinated drinks, or sugary fruit juices, which can worsen diarrhea, and withhold solid foods while the child is vomiting. Once the stomach has settled, slowly reintroduce bland foods using the BRAT diet (bananas, rice, applesauce, toast).

- In case of food poisoning adult antidiarrheal medications (e.g., loperamide or Pepto-Bismol) should never be given to children, as they can trap toxins in the body and prolong the illness.

- In cases of severe illness or severe dehydration, the patient should be referred for hospital treatment.

Conclusion.

The multiple antigenic types and mild course of enterovirus infections make vaccine development pointless (with the exception of polio vaccine). Unfortunately, benign encephalitis caused by EV has evolved in recent years and is characterized by a worse prognosis. For this reason, a vaccine against non-polio EV is being developed in China^[18]. Quarantine is not effective due to the high incidence of congenital infections and mass carriage in healthy individuals (17-46% during the summer months) ^[4,9,18,22]. The most important measures to prevent infectious diseases, whether viral or bacterial, are: Strict hygiene and washing hands as often as possible and drinking mineral or spring water, as tap water is associated with numerous gastrointestinal problems, so it is best to avoid it. Buying food from the street is risky. Buy food only from the grocery store, because all storage conditions are met there and their quality and origin are guaranteed. Canned food that is damaged, food with initial signs of spoilage or food that has not been refrigerated should not be consumed. It is important not to leave food warm for more than 3 hours in the summer, especially meat and dairy products, as they spoil faster, i.e. food products and ready-made foods should only be stored in refrigerated conditions. Correct thermal processing of food must be observed - do not consume semi-raw or undercooked meat, eggs and dairy products. After defrosting or warming, the dish should not be cooled or frozen again. Vegetables and fruits should be washed before consumption, as high temperature and humidity create good conditions for the reproduction of microorganisms both in food products and in the environment and favor the development of bacterial infections - food poisoning.

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